

IPR Management Plan

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
H2020-MSCA-ITN-2014
Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions

Project no.: 642877
Project acronym: InnoChain
Project title: Building Innovation in the Extended Digital Chain

Start date of the project: 01/09/2015
Duration of the project: 48 months

Workpackage: 1 - Management
Task: 1.4

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this task: ITKE
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Background

According to the Annex 1 to the GA, Part B, “IPR is managed by the IPR management plan (WP 1.4). The agreement is outlined at proposal stage following a background-foreground model. It will be fully consolidated as part of the Review of Requirements. Partners will sign a Consortium Agreement managing the knowledge produced. The plan will be outlined within 6 months of the project start and submitted to Steering Committee for approval.” (p. 33).

The aim of the IPR Management Plan is to ensure that IPR is shared in relevant way between Beneficiaries, ESR's and Industry Partners.

This aim is pursued in the following steps:

1. Preparation of a common IPR Industry Partner Agreement Template ('Agreement').

The aim of the `Agreement` is to provide a common starting point for the negotiations of the Beneficiaries, the ESR and their respective Industry Partners about IPR issues.

- The `Agreement` template is prepared by UCL and ITKE. The `Agreement` is checked by the legal administration of UCL and ITKE. *Task completed.*
- The `Agreement` is forwarded to the coordinator (CITA). The coordinator checks the `Agreement` with KADK's legal administration and ensures that the `Agreement` is in alignment with the Grant Agreement, the consortium agreement and the Research Executive Agency (REA). *Task completed: see attached document*
- The `Agreement` is forwarded by the coordinator (CITA) to all beneficiaries. All beneficiaries check the Agreement with their respective legal administrations. *Task completed 10.03.2016.*

2. Negotiation and settlement of `Agreement` with Industry Partners

The aim of the `Agreement` is to record the collaboration between the Beneficiaries and their respective Industry Partners on the Early Stage Researcher position under the rules laid down by the Research Executive Agency (REA).

- The `Agreement` is forwarded by the beneficiaries to their respective Industry Partner(s). The terms and conditions of the `Agreement` are negotiated. The

`Agreement' has to be signed before any exchange of knowledge takes place between the parties. *Task due: before first exchange of knowledge between partners*

- A copy of the accepted and signed `Agreement' is forwarded to the coordinator (CITA). Deviations from the common Model Agreement are marked. *Task due: before first exchange of knowledge between partners*
- The coordinator (CITA) keeps a record of the 'Agreements' and checks whether the negotiated 'Agreement' is in accordance with the Grant Agreement, the consortium agreement and the Research Executive Agency (REA). Any inconsistencies are brought to the Supervisory Board.